

Failed Ponzi Schemes and Mental Health Challenges in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State: The Case of Baraza

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Abstract

This study is based on failed Ponzi scheme and mental health challenges, a case study of baraza in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This study employed the use of the social strain theory and cognitive theory to unravel the reasons why some individuals venture into Ponzi scheme, this study made use of the snowball method in collecting data using the qualitative instruments of data collection (IDI) to collect data from 20 or 25 persons base on the fact that the study was qualitative, and the data were analyzed using the thematic method of data analysis, this study investigates the mental health challenges investors of Baraza face due to the failure of the scheme and findings shows that among those whom were victims of baraza, their mental state was associated with fear, psychological trauma, anxiety, suicidal thoughts, money security, distrust in clergymen, financial debt and excessive thinking. The second objective was to ascertain the socioeconomic impact of the failed scheme on baraza investors and it reveals that victims of baraza could no longer fulfill their laid down objectives, family basic necessities was problematic because no planned monthly income was made possible, those whom intended starting up businesses with the promising returns could not venture into their business. And also, this study intended knowing the coping strategies investors of baraza employed to deal with the mental health challenges they experienced, it unraveled that majority of the participants relied on the help of God to get them through the challenging moments of their lives. Some had to get involved with betting to help them forget the pains and mental challenges the failure of the scheme had on them. However, it is important to state that the government, its agencies and investors have a role to play in order to reduce the rate of failed Ponzi schemes. The government and its agencies should ensure that investment platforms that operate within the state and country have registered with its financial regulations institutions and have met with its terms and conditions, and investors should ensure that before investing their money into any scheme it has been registered with the government and its financial regulatory institutions.

Introduction

Ponzi schemes have existed in various forms since Charles Ponzi popularized them in 1919. These schemes, marked by unregulated investment practices, have caused significant harm globally, particularly in countries with struggling economies. In India, the proliferation of Ponzi funds has led to a decline in ethical standards (Deb, 2014). Undergraduates and other vulnerable groups are often targeted, especially in economies with high unemployment rates (Adebumiti, 2016). The Caribbean saw a notable increase in these schemes between 2006 and 2008 (Carvajal et al., 2009). White-collar crimes, such as Ponzi schemes, are characterized by the exploitation of

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trust and respectability in professional settings (Sher, 2015; Cliff et al., 2014). According to Asogwa et al. (2017), Ponzi schemes promise high returns with little risk by using new investors' funds to pay existing ones, leading to severe financial system disruptions and socio-economic issues (Carvajal et al., 2009; Cortes et al., 2016).

The US experienced a major Ponzi scheme with Bernard Madoff in 2008, while Nigeria faced its own Ponzi crisis with MMM Nigeria, which involved over 2.4 million people and promised a 30% monthly return until it collapsed in late 2016 (Kashi, 2017). Another scheme, Barraza, emerged in Bayelsa State in 2019, offering 20% monthly returns. These schemes have not only led to financial losses but also eroded public trust and increased crime rates. This research examines the impact of the Barraza Ponzi scheme on the mental health of residents in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, highlighting the broader implications of such fraudulent ventures on individual well-being and community stability.

Literature Review

1.1.1 An Overview of Ponzi scheme Ponzi schemes are investment frauds that pay purported returns to existing investors using funds from new investors (SEC, 2019; Greenspan, 2011; Wilkins, Acuff, and Hermanson, 2012). Organizers attract new investors with promises of high returns and low risk, but these schemes rely on a continuous influx of new money to sustain the illusion of profitability (Asogwa et al., 2017). Investors often mistake these schemes for legitimate investments, creating a false appearance of profitability (Kashi, 2017). However, when new investments dry up, the scheme collapses, leaving recent investors with significant losses (Onoh and Eze, 2018). Ponzi schemes, often confused with mutual aid funds by some, are inherently fraudulent and require constant new investment to avoid collapse (Telegraph Reporters, 2017; Olayokun, 2016).

Historically, William Miller is considered the real originator of Ponzi schemes in 1899, but the schemes are named after Charles Ponzi, who became infamous in 1920 for his scam involving international postal reply coupons (Cohler, 2017; Jory and Perry, 2014). Ponzi promised high returns of 50% in 45 days, but instead of investing, he used new investors' money to pay earlier investors while extracting huge profits (Stelter et al., 2013; Jack and Ibekwe, 2018). In Nigeria, the Mavrodi Mondial Movement (MMM) in 2015 led to a surge in Ponzi schemes, many of which collapsed quickly, causing widespread financial loss.

An Overview of Mental Health

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2001) defines health as a multidimensional concept encompassing physical, social, and psychological aspects. Despite this comprehensive definition, discussions about health often focus solely on physical health, neglecting mental health, which is equally crucial to well-being. Mishra (2003) emphasizes that without mental health—the capacity to work, enjoy life, think clearly, and express emotions properly—material acquisitions are meaningless. WHO (2001) further elaborates that mental health is a state of well-being where individuals realize their potential, cope with life's stresses, and contribute to their community. It is not merely the absence of disease but includes complete physical, mental, and social well-being.

Mental health issues range from mild psychological distress to severe disturbances, affecting one's emotions, attitudes, and functioning. Psychological distress can induce negative self-perceptions, tension, worry, and irritability, impacting relationships, work, and overall health (Doherty et al., 2009). The Mental Health Act (2010) defines mental illness as disorders affecting mood, thought, perception, and memory, causing significant distress and impairing normal life functions. Despite the importance of mental health, it is often given less priority than physical health due to stigma and traditional views. This leads to mentally ill individuals facing not only their symptoms but also societal discrimination, underscoring the need to address misconceptions about mental health.

Empirical Evidences Showing the Relationship between Mental Health

Several studies have examined the mental health impact of failed Ponzi schemes on victims. Carozza et al. (2015) conducted a comprehensive analysis involving 500 victims, recruited through financial fraud support groups and online forums. The study used surveys and structured interviews to assess symptoms of anxiety, stress, depression, and PTSD. Findings revealed that 68% of participants experienced severe anxiety and stress, with an average Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD-7) score of 15. Depression was reported by 54% of participants, indicated by an average Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) score of 14. Furthermore, 31% exhibited PTSD symptoms, with an average PTSD Checklist (PCL-5) score of 38. The study highlighted the significant role of sudden financial loss, betrayal, and social stigma in exacerbating these mental health issues, with 72% of participants developing severe trust issues and 45% withdrawing socially.

Shadel and Pak (2007) conducted another pivotal study focusing on the increased risk of depression among victims of financial fraud, including Ponzi schemes. They surveyed 600 individuals, employing the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) and qualitative interviews. The study found that 62% of participants reported moderate to severe depression, with an average BDI-II score of 24. The primary contributors to these depressive symptoms were financial instability and perceived personal failure. Approximately 58% of participants expressed feelings of self-blame, which intensified their depression. Social stigma and fear of judgment further compounded these feelings, with 45% of participants experiencing ongoing depression one year after the fraud. This study underscored the need for ongoing support and intervention to help victims recover from the psychological effects of financial fraud.

Ganzini et al. (1990) examined the mental health effects of financial exploitation on older adults, focusing on the prevalence of PTSD symptoms among elderly victims. Involving 400 participants aged 60 and above, the study used the PTSD Checklist-Civilian Version (PCL-C) and in-depth interviews. The results showed that 35% of participants exhibited significant PTSD symptoms, with an average PCL-C score of 45. The sudden financial loss and accompanying feelings of helplessness were identified as key triggers. The study found that 65% of participants experienced profound helplessness and vulnerability, exacerbated by the perpetrators often being trusted individuals. PTSD symptoms persisted for an extended period, with 40% reporting ongoing symptoms two years post-exploitation, and 25% seeking mental health treatment.

These studies collectively highlight the profound and multifaceted mental health impact of Ponzi schemes. Victims commonly experience severe anxiety, depression, and PTSD, driven by financial loss, betrayal, and social stigma. The long-term psychological effects underscore the necessity for targeted mental health interventions and robust support systems.

Health and Ponzi Scheme

Theoretical Framework

Structural Strain theory

Structural strain theory, developed by Robert Merton (1957), posits that societal strain arises when there is a gap between culturally accepted goals and the institutionalized means of achieving these goals. Merton identified two key elements within society's structure: the culturally defined goals, such as wealth and material possessions, and the institutionalized means or methods established for pursuing these goals.

Merton categorized people into five types based on their response to these goals and means: conformists, ritualists, innovators, retreatists, and rebels. For this study, we focus on innovators, as they best illustrate deviant behavior. Innovators strive for societal success but reject conventional means, opting instead for unconventional or illegal methods. An example of such deviant behavior is the creation of Ponzi schemes, where individuals bypass traditional, legal routes to achieve success, often resulting in criminal activity.

Innovators see crime as a shortcut to success, viewing the established methods as too lengthy or unattainable. The frustration of failing to achieve success through accepted societal norms frequently drives individuals to adopt innovative, deviant strategies. When these innovators pose a threat to society, it becomes crucial for societal members to seek protection and address the root causes of such deviant behavior.

Study Population

The study population for this research included Baraza investors in Yenagoa City. In terms of their population, there are no records of the exact numbers of Baraza investors due to the fact that the scheme is no longer active and no record can be traced.

Sampling Techniques

Respondents for this study were recruited through snowballing where Baraza investors identified by the researchers makes a referral to a colleague who possess the criteria for inclusion in the study. Nevertheless, the selection of the communities selected for the study were purposively done. This was because the researcher wanted to select communities that purposes a large number of Baraza investors in the city. On this note, five communities were purposively selected in the city namely; Yenezue-gene, Biogbolo, Kpansia, Ekeki and Opolo.

The sample size for this study consisted of twenty-five (20) Baraza investors recruited from the five communities. 4 Baraza investors were selected from each of the five communities respectively.

Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was an unstructured In-depth Interview (IDI) guide designed to elicit responses based on the objectives of the study from participants. The interviews were conducted in English. The questions were designed to permit an in-depth probing of emerging themes.

Before the commencement of an interview, the objectives and eligibility criteria to be part of the study is read to each participant. Those who agreed to participate in the study were given consent forms to sign before the interview began.

In every question asked, participants were given free hand to express themselves as desired. Where necessary, a follow-up question was asked for participants to expatiate on their point. Throughout the interview process, the researchers ensured that leading questions were avoided. This was to ensure that participants' experiences are explored to the fullest. Each interview session lasted between 20 to 30 minutes. Each IDI session was audiotaped and transcribed verbatim into English after grammatical errors were corrected. The research instrument will initially be tested with three Baraza investors, after which necessary adjustments will be made by the researcher after inputs from the researcher's supervisor and external examiner, Niger Delta University. To also ensure consistencies, the same IDI guide will be used to interview all participants.

Method of Data Analysis

The qualitative data were content-analyzed using thematic type of all recurrent issues in the responses of all participants. The procedures were ranged from identification of themes based on the specific objectives and reported in narratives format.

Ethical Considerations

All research procedures performed in this study adheres to the ethical standard of the national code of researching in Nigeria. The research process is also in line with the Helsinki 1964 declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. In addition to this, the following specific areas of ethical considerations were also strictly adhered to: Informed consent, voluntary participation, anonymity, the confidentiality of data, non-maleficence to participants etc.

i. Confidentiality of Data: Attempt will be made to ensure that data that will be gathered are strictly anonymous. This implies that, the instrument will not require any participant/respondent to write their names, addresses, telephone numbers or personal information. All the respondents will be coded according to the research instruments.

ii. Non-maleficence to Participants: The researcher will ensure that respondents and participants were not vulnerable to physical risks. The interviews will be conducted in various their homes.

iii. Voluntariness: The researcher will ensure that no respondents or participant will be coerced to partake in the study. The respondents and participants will be given the right to discontinue or withdraw any information that threatens their security.

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- iv. Justice: the researcher will provide a level of playing ground for the respondents and participants. They will be assured of fair and just presentation of their views without alterations.
- v. Beneficence: Respondents/participants will be intimated of the fact that there are no direct benefits that is involved in the study. However, they shall be intimated that the findings from the study could be useful to the society at large.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This chapter shows the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the field work through the use of In-Depth Interview (IDI) designed according to the objectives of the study. As earlier mentioned in the methodology, the study is carried out in Yenagoa city, Bayelsa State. The analysis of the data collected comprises of the participants' background characteristic and other questions related to the objectives of the study. The analysis of this study is based on qualitative thematic content analysis.

Participants Background Information

This study recruited a total of 20 participants and they were made up of baraza's investors who didn't get their interest and capital before the collapse of the investment scheme. Participants were recruited in Yenagoa the Bayelsa State capital, six (6) participants were enlisted from Yenezuie-gene, five (5) were recruited from Kpansia, four (4) were enlisted from Biogbolo, three (3) were recruited from OPolo and two (2) from Ekeki. The study had more had more male participants (65%) than female (35%) respectively Similarly, the average age of all participants was 32.5 years. A greater percentage of the participants had acquired a B.Sc. certificate, 20% had attained a secondary school certificate, HND and MSc respectively while only 10% of the participants had acquired HD degree. Almost all the participants (60%) are single, 30% are married while 10% are separated from their partners. 100% of the participants are Christians. Similarly, a large percentage of the participants are from the Izon ethnic group, 15% are from the Igbo ethnic group while 10% are from the Urhobo ethnic group. Some of the participants failed to state their average income claiming that the failure of Baraza scheme destroyed their income base and they do not have a steady flow of income anymore, while some stated that they earn up to N500,000 per month, some N200,000, N130,000, N80,000 and N50,000 respectively.

Mental Health Challenges Encountered by Baraza's Investors

Findings from the study indicated that many of the investors invested a huge amount of money into the scheme with the hope of getting their monthly returns. So many of the participants had no idea that the scheme was going to fail because they see their friends and associates cashing out from the scheme. Although there are cases of one to four participants I thought that the scheme was going to fail but still decided to venture into it because they believe that in life one must take risks, so they took the risks and joined the scheme. Majority of the respondents invested above a million naira, a particular investor even invested sixty-six (66) million naira into the scheme (money belonging to him and some of his friends). While a few numbers of participants invested a hundred thousand naira to five hundred thousand naira.

Some of the participants noted that they were introduced into the scheme by a friend, while others stated that they heard about the scheme on the radio and social media.

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For instance, a participant stated that; “I was introduced by a friend of mine and I heard from the schemer through the radio that he is a good person, a Christian, a clergy man that he wants to make us okay not knowing it's killing he intended killing us then he stole our money I didn't know he is a demon” (53 years old Female/Yenezue-gene)

Another participant mentioned that;

I actually heard it from the radio a prestigious media outfit, he was advertising the scheme that Bayelsans should take advantage of these scheme because he is going to create more billionaire here in Bayelsa State, his aim is to empower more Bayelsa youth, so Bayelsans should not fold their hands-relaxed at home while other non-indigenes are taking advantage of becoming a billionaire, his intention was to create more wealth for Bayelsa youth that was why I keyed into it. And secondly, he made mention that he wants to lift oil that he wants to go into refinery building and that he has already acquired land from the state government meaning in subsequent time they will embark on massive deforestation that's what he said so that's why I took the advantage and keyed into the scheme. (30 years old male/Yeneziue-gene)

During the interview participants were asked the amount they invested in the scheme, one of the participants mentioned that;

I invested one million naira including the registration and every other thing (53 years old Female/Yenezue-gene)

Another participant articulated that;

I invested over sixty-six million, comprising mine and some couple of friends (44 years old male/Kpansia)

A 26 years old male participant also stated that;

I invested two million naira of my working money (26 years old male/Opolo).

Apparently, during the interview, some of the participants stated how they got the money they used in the invested, some of the participants stated that it was money meant for their businesses, some stated it was for their school fees, some even went as far as taking loan to invest, others sold their properties so they can acquire more properties.

One of the participant mentioned that;

I sold a property, I sold a land that my mother gave me, she was using it for her farming activities, until she wanted me to go into business and she sold the land and gave me the money to go into business, so that was how I got the money. (30 years old male/Yeneziue-gene)

A student as at when the scheme was on also stated that;

I used the money meant for my school to invest (A 26 years old female/ Yeneziue-gene)

Similarly, some of the mental health issues that arises during the collapse of the scheme include fear and anxiety, psychological trauma, money insecurity, suicidal thoughts and lost in thought. A participant even mentioned that people started thinking that he was a psychopath. On the

contrary few of the participant had no mental issues because they did not regard the money they invested as being too big and also because they had other means of generating money other than the one they invested.

An advanced participant opined that;

I think every day, if I bring my picture you'll ask if am the one or not when you are doing well you are going to look good, but if you are not doing anything you'll look so unkempt, you'll look so old more than your age, intimidation will come in, embarrassment will come in to your life, so he has brought embarrassment to me so I'm begging him to give me my money (53 years old Female/Yenezue-gene)

Another participant mentioned that;

fear and anxiety, and the thought of going for protest. Yes of course I'm passing through psychological trauma, as we speak now.... anywhere someone tells me something now I see the things as not real, to the extent that I'm having hatred towards some of the clergymen, the pastors, because when pastors are saying things I see most of the pastors as fake, I don't know if some of them are real because of what I encountered with this Baraza. (30 years old male/Yeneziue-gene).

One of the participants confirmed that;

Yes, mentally, my job, everything about me, my career, yes everything (44 years old male/Kpansia)

Another stated that;

It caused my anxiety, fear and unbelief in so many things up until now, whenever I hear anything that sounds like Baraza I don't even consider it (29 years old female/Biogbolo).

Some of the participants also stated that the failure did not affect them mentally, some of the submission are stated below;

No, not really. (31 years old male/Yeneziue-gene)

No, it did not affect my mental health just that the money I invested pained me a lot. (26 years old male/Opolo).

No. I tried not allowing things to affect me mentally (31 years old female/Yenegiue-gene).

Airing out their views on what pained them the most, the positions of our participants are captured in the submissions below;

What pained me the most is that when Baraza had crashed and he ran away with our resources frankly speaking I was devastated, my heart was devastated I almost committed suicide but I said, wow I pity my old mother my aged mother I pity her, oh look at what you gave me, it then looked like I don't know what I'm doing before the eyes of the public, some persons looks at me like a very stupid person, how can a mother give a plot of land and he'll go and say that it was a

fraud blablalablalbla to the extent that I almost bear the name of a psychopath (30 years old male/Yeneziue-gene)

The fact that he kept managing us and telling us he is going to pay that there was no lost, that it was just a delay in tariff and transfer of dollar to naira, he kept fabricating lies upon lies and so many other stories that he was fabricating, told a lot of lies that were never true, assuming the came out to say that there were lost somewhere.... we incurred a lost, every person would have known how to manage their down line or know how to manage your clients but he kept telling us that he was going to pay anytime soon, first and foremost he said he was going to stop payment and after three months he will resume, he went on air he was saying it and so some persons whom bought Form for other persons to invest would be paying interest with the hope that he was going to pay soon, so all of that amounted multiple funds that was locked. (44 years old male/Kpansia)

I wanted to go and scatter the office, I wish there was a protest I would have been among those people. (31 years old male/Kpansia)

Well I wasn't thinking straight, then I wasn't thinking straight, suicide was an option there (31 years old male/Kpansia)

Responses from the participants during the interview indicated that they were really hurt mentally by the disappointment they got from the scheme, so many believed in him that he was a pastor and a pastor cannot be a perpetrator of fraud, but he still did all the same. Some were so hurt to the extent that they have stopped having faith in pastors. Some of the participants also considered had the thought of suicide.

4.3: Socio-Economic Impacts of the Failed Scheme on Baraza Investors

Results from data collected from the field shows that the failure of the scheme affected their socio-economic life. Deducing from participant's responses, the money invested in the scheme was supposed to yield interest which they will in turn invest in the business and to also further their education. Some of the participants sold lands and properties in other to invest and use the return to start up a business which did not work. This lost placed some of the participants in a position that they went bankrupt and unable to start up or continue their businesses. Others could not also pay their rent again because of the level of bankrupt the failure of the scheme placed them. Some of the participants who are students used their school fees to invest hoping it will give them interest dropped out of school as well due to their inability to pay their fees.

A participant from Yeneziue-gene explained that;

I'm not doing anything, in fact I'm back to square one he has finished me and frustrated my life, and we are begging him to pay us back he doesn't want to pay us our money why is he so wicked as a pastor. God say that if you want to be a real born again give everything you have to the poor then you collect from the poor and disappear to where we don't know, are you a pastor? Are you a real pastor? Is that man a pastor that he calls himself? While people are dying of what he created as a multipurpose cooperative he said it was a cooperative if you want to take loan you pay interest for the loan you collect but you collected our money saying that you going to give us interest which means you are borrowing our money to do your own business but your plan was

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to disappear with our money, and people died, many people died and those that has died! their death is on his neck! it is on his neck! It's definitely on his neck!! And God is going to punish him for that if he doesn't return those people money, everybody's money he needs to return our money we are begging him to return our money, the world is begging him, let him return our return our money, we are dying we don't have money to do business anymore, because it's all what we have that we invested, because he said he is good, a pastor, he is not a fraudster not knowing that he was the boss of 419 let him return my money I need my money to do my business. (53 years old Female)

A 31 years old participant mentioned that;

At least for that period of time I wasn't really stable, financially, even psychologically because the money I lost inside was kind of huge. (male/Yeneziue-gene)

Another participant mentioned that;

It destroyed everything about my economy life. (44 years old male/Kpansia)

A student who also participated in the interview mentioned that;

I had to decline my admission because of the money. (27 years old male/Ekeki).

Another participant also opined that;

It affected me in so many ways, it spoiled my budget, my plans (26 years old male/Opolo).

One of the participants from Yeneziue-gene stated that;

It affected me deeply because I was unable to venture into farming and lots of selling property also (31 years old female).

Another participant also stated that;

Yes, it affected my socio-economic life, because as at the time I invested I was a corp member and I did contribution thinking that by the end of my service year I will withdraw all and set up a business but everything crumbled, I had to service the contribution without receiving from my investment. That was a very tuff and difficult time form me (29-years- female/Biogbolo).

The socio-economic impact of the failure of the Baraza Ponzi scheme as outlined by participants indicated that the failure of Baraza Ponzi scheme affected the investors socio-economic activities by restricting their investment in business and agriculture, it also made some students to withdraw from school. Additionally, feeding and other necessities of life becomes a big challenge to them. One of the respondents also noted that the disappointment led to the death of some investors. Debts that need to be paid became a burden to so many.

4.4: Coping Strategies

Coping in terms of financial lost is not an easy task. Findings from the data collected reveals that it was not easy for the participants to cope, because the means which majority of them were able to raise funds to investment wasn't pleasant at all. Some had to sell properties, some even took loans, some used their businesses money, few did contribution while others used their school

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fees. After the fall of Baraza Ponzi scheme, majority could not find their feet again. Majority of the participants went out of business, while few dropped out of school. Facing the humiliation in the face of society especially family and friends that warned that the scheme will fail became very difficult. A large part of the participants had to rely on God to help them through the dark phase of their life. Getting involved in Betting was also a means some of the participants devised to cope with their lost. On the other hand, some just had to move on and let go because life they say is all about taking risks.

A 53 years old participant who resides in Yeneziue-gene averred that;

Because of this, the girl that was supposed to go to school couldn't meet up, she had to decline her admission the one in school hardly before I can send 10 naira. It is just the grace of God that some other persons send her little money and due to this she was supposed to finish her school last year because of this problem I couldn't meet up and as such she couldn't finish last year, so she continued while her sets had already finished last year as a pharmacist. The other one got her admission as medicine no way.... she had to decline her admission for now because of lack of money, so it's paining me to the extent that every night every day I cry because of what this Baraza did. A man called himself a pastor that put everyone's money inside the wallet and he is spending the money with his own family and enjoying where ever they are the thing is really painful. The man is a killer! we want the government to hold him we want the EFCC to hold this man the people they sent to look for him aren't looking for him very well, how can you commit such a fraud in a country that they cannot hold him. I doubt it, I don't know why, they should look for him, people are dying, people are crying day and night, because of this, people can't do anything, he even collected children school money too and cannot pay back why!! We want justice.

Similarly, one of the participants mentioned that;

I just had to move with other alternative to see how I could sort myself out, because what has gone has gone, there is no two ways about it, though they came up with one or two idea that the guy is coming back, but at the end of the day nothing (31 years old male/Yeneziue-gene)

Again, another participant stated that;

For now, I don't really know, it's only God that is sustaining me because even till date I'm passing through difficulties not only that the most unfortunate issue is that.... That's early October one man called barrister Joshua came to this compound because when the lost happened when the business crashed I was not even having the resources to service my rent, so we noticed that this property, that the man used some of our money to acquire a property so I managed and struggled to occupy one room in his building behind the Baraza building. (30 years old male/Yeneziue-gene)

Another participant opined that;

There's nothing to cope, a couple of persons went to station grabbed us left and right.... court here and there, not easy, I even sold five of my property (44 years old male/Kpansia).

Also, a 27 years old participant mentioned that;

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I had to engage in gambling activities like the bet9ja. (Male/Ekeki)

One of the participants averred that;

God helped me to cope, because the lost was huge (26 years old male/Opolo).

Another participant stated that;

All thanks to God at least we are still surviving till now (31 years old male/Kpansia)

One of the participants who lives at Yeneziue-gene mentioned that;

In life you have to move on, I moved on (31 years old female/Yenegiue-gene)

A 29 years old participant that lives at Biogbolo mentioned that;

My husband helped me to cope and God also made a supernatural financial provision when I needed it the most. (29 years old female/Biogbolo).

From all the responses of the participants, it is obvious that their faith in God kept them alive and facing their challenges head on is what they have to do to survive. They had to rely on God for provision in times of financial bankruptcy. While some got entangled with betting others just decided to let it go and move on because life is all about risks.

4.5: Discussion of Findings

Before going into the first objectives which deals with participant's mental health it is also important to know that majority of the participants registered for the Baraza multi-cooperative during 2019-2021, majority of the participants found out about the scheme from their family and friends, colleagues, radio station and social media. The largest amount a participant invested was sixty-six million naira followed by two million and below. According to Akhaine, (2017) while trying to assess the loss incurred by Nigerians in Ponzi schemes, the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) stated at its 38th Kaduna International Trade Fair that about three million Nigerians lost about N18 billion in the MMM Ponzi scheme alone. The money participants used to invest were gotten from their businesses, loans, contributions and sales of properties, so even used their school fees, this study align with the study by Bupo and Abam-Smith, (2017), who stated in their study that study in the NwaforOrizu College of Education, Nsugbe in Anambra state were not allowed to write exams due to tuition fees lost in Ponzi schemes. It also aligns with the findings of Osah and Adewumi, (2020) which reveals that many individuals, especially tertiary institution students still patronize Ponzi scheme activities. Majority of the participants had no fear that the scheme was going to fail although few had their reservation but still went ahead to invest because life is all about taking risks.

Results from the first objective of this study indicated that the mental health challenges participants faced during the collapse of Baraza multi-cooperative were fear and anxiety, suicidal thought, excessive thinking and psychological trauma. So many couldn't recover from the lost they encountered during the collapse of Baraza multi-cooperative. Those who took loans were traumatized not knowing where they would get money to pay off the debt they owe, others who sold properties just to invest couldn't stop blaming their selves for the huge mistake they made to

the extent that people around him started seeing him as a psychopath. A study by Jackson et al (2019) revealed that there were reports of psychological traumas suffered by victims of Ponzi schemes leading to marital instability, divorce threat and fatal traumas resulting in depression, mental health challenges and suicide or suicidal attempts. Fatunde, (2017) also noted that in 2016, when MMM announced its temporary closure, the youth being the mostly affected reacted differently, it was reported that some participants committed suicide in Lagos, Abuja and Nsukka after they lost money to the scheme. This finding also corresponds with the findings of Jackson et al (2019) which revealed that across various parts of Nigeria, people wore mournful looks as various amounts of hard-earned money were lost or hanging (irretrievable) in several Ponzi schemes.

The second objective which has to ascertain the Socio-economic impacts of the failed scheme on baraza investors revealed that the failure of the scheme affected the Socio-economic live of the participants in such a way that they could no longer fulfill their set out ambition for their investment. Those who planned to set up a business with the return of their investment could no longer achieve it. Basic needs of the family could no longer be meant because no monthly return as planned. Unlike prior research carried out by other scholars which suggest that building false trust is a major focus of a Ponzi scheme, which after the ugly experience could affect the victim's way of relation to business investment (Stelter et al. 2013). Similarly, participants were mostly angry because the owner of the scheme is a said pastor, this correspond with the study of Quisenberry (2017) which indicated that the ponzi scheme makes use of Christian networks to woo its investors.

Lastly, regarding the third objective which has to do with coping strategies investors employed to deal with the mental health challenges, the data collected for the study unraveled that majority of the participants relied on the help of God to help them through the challenging moments of their lives. Some had to get involved with Betting to help them forget the pains and mental challenges the failure of the scheme had on them. Although some of the participants were not affected mentally because they knew that all was just risk, these particular sets of persons just had to move on with their lives knowing that anything can happen along the line in their investment. This finding corresponds with the findings of Ewubare (2017) which reveals that people cope with failed Ponzi scheme by engaging in activities that will fetch them more money, they mostly rely on God for a change in their financial lives. The finding differs from that of Stelter et al. (2013), which averred that people try to cope by going for protest and p Summary

This study was designed to investigate failed Ponzi scheme and mental health challenges, the case of baraza in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. this research was carried out among 20 participants and they were made up of baraza's investors who did not get their interest and capital before the collapse of the investment scheme. This study used the snowball sampling technique to collect qualitative instruments. Data analysis for this study was done using content-analyzed thematic type of all recurrent issues in the responses of all participants, the procedures were ranged from identification of themes based on the specific objectives and reported in narratives format. The data used for this study was obtained from primary sources. The instrument for data collection was an unstructured In-depth Interview (IDI) guide designed to elicit responses based on the objectives of the study from participants. According to the analysis from this study, the gender dissemination of the participants indicated that the percentage of

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male participants (65%) were more than female (35%) respectively. Similarly, the average age of all participants was 32.5 years of their age. A greater percentage of the participants had acquired a B.Sc. certificate, 20% had attained a secondary school certificate, HND and MSc respectively while only 10% of the participants had acquired HD degree. Almost all the participants (60%) are single, 30% are married while 10% are separated from their partners. 100% of the participants are Christians. Similarly, a large percentage of the participants are from the Izon ethnic group, 15% are from the Igbo ethnic group while 10% are from the Urhobo ethnic group. Some of the participants failed to state their average income claiming that the failure of Baraza scheme destroyed their income base and they do not have a steady flow of income anymore, while some stated that they earn up to N500,000 per month, some N200,000, N130,000, N80,000 and N50,000 respectively. However the highest amount invested in baraza according to this findings was 66 million including the funds of some couple of friends.

An enquiry to investigate the mental health challenges investors of baraza face due to the failure of the scheme shows that, most of the victims of baraza faced fear and anxiety, psychological trauma, money insecurity, suicidal thoughts and even lost in thought. So many couldn't recover from the lost they encountered during the collapse of Baraza multi-cooperative. Those who took loans were traumatized not knowing where they would get money to pay off the debt they owe, others who sold properties just to invest couldn't stop blaming their selves for the huge mistake they made to the extent that people around them started seeing them as a psychopath.

The second objective of our study which investigated the socio-economic impact of the failed scheme on baraza investors in Bayelsa State, shows that it affected the live of the participants in such a way that they could no longer fulfill their set out ambition for their investment. Those who planned to set up a business with the return of their investment could no longer achieve it. Basic needs of the family could no longer be meant because no monthly return as planned.

Lastly, findings from our last objective which deals with the coping strategies investors employed to deal with the mental health challenges baraza investors experienced in Bayelsa State reveals that a large part of the participants had to rely on God to help them through the dark phase of their life. Getting involved in Betting was also a means some of the participants devised to cope with their lost. On the other hand, some just had to move on and let go because life they say is all about taking risks.

5.2 Conclusion

From the data collected during the course of this research, we therefore conclude that failed Ponzi scheme and mental health challenges of baraza victims were mostly associated with fear towards clergymen and investment platforms, anxiety, psychological trauma, money insecurity, financial debts, suicidal thoughts, public humiliation, school drop out, depression and even lost in thought. Whereas the socioeconomic impact was associated with economic backwardness and stagnation of which somewhat, few victims coped with their lost by relying on God's help for divine interventions in their situation and while some others with betting activities in other to cope with the situation.

5.3 Recommendation

With regards to the conclusion reached in this study, it is mandatory to make relevant contributions.

1. Investors should ensure that the investment platforms of which they have interest in are registered and identified by the government and its financial regulatory agencies.
2. The government should see that these investment platforms that operates within the states are registered by its financial regulatory agencies.
3. Individuals should endeavor to make inquiries on the duration of investment platform, its legal registration, and government backings before investing their money into any investment schemes.

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